

**XIth BALKAN CONGRESS OF
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&
abstracts***

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INVITED SPEAKER - ABSTRACTS

Mediastinal masses in children are often symptomatic and can have a varied symptomatology and etiology. The most common symptoms at presentation are dyspnea, cough, fever, aching pain and general malaise. Children may also present with recurrent pulmonary infections. Constitutional symptoms may be associated with neoplasia or infection. Respiratory symptoms and dysphagia can occur due to bronchial and esophageal obstruction respectively. A mediastinal mass may also result in a compression of the superior vena cava (superior vena cava syndrome), Horner's syndrome, or hoarseness (due to compression of left laryngeal nerve). Many mediastinal masses are asymptomatic and are an incidental finding on chest radiographs.

Over 50% of pediatric mediastinal masses are malignant and as a result need to be investigated thoroughly. If a malignancy is suspected, a referral to an oncologist is warranted.

Three different cases of children presented with acute symptoms due to mediastinal pathology will be reviewed.

Clinical symptoms, questions to ask and algorithm of radiological investigations will be presented.

Author: **Biljana Markovic Vasiljkovic**

Subject: **Genitourinary**

Title: **PIRADS system-a new paradigm**

INTRODUCTION: Prostate cancer is the second most common neoplasm in male population. Modern approach to loco-regional staging of prostate cancer involves selection of the optimum diagnostic procedure. Beside transrectal ultrasound biopsy, different magnetic resonance modalities are used in order to obtain an accurate diagnosis for each stage.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: In our work we will review the available literature and the latest urology and radiology protocols for the treatment of prostate carcinoma led by ESUR's recommendation from year 2012 which are based upon MRI examinations.

DISCUSSION: Increased incidence of prostate cancer in the last decade (early screening) with increasing availability of imaging techniques enabled the new setting criteria for TN staging of prostate cancer. The European Society of Urogenital Radiology of (ESUR) recommended the PI RADS classification of prostate cancer with very precisely defined radiological, morphological, clinical and laboratory parameters for prostate carcinoma.

CONCLUSION: Given the high incidence of prostate cancer, accurate staging is imperative for the selection of appropriate methods of treatment, and the possibility of comparison and tracking patients.

Author: **Milena Spirovski**

Subject: **Genitourinary**

Title: **Multiparametric prostate cancer imaging**

Despite recent improvements in detection and treatment, prostate cancer continues to be the most common malignancy in men, and one of the leading causes of cancer death. The major goal for prostate cancer imaging is more accurate disease characterization through the synthesis of anatomic, functional and molecular imaging information.

Conventional magnetic resonance (MR) imaging allows unparalleled anatomic assessment of the prostate with better soft tissue resolution than any other imaging modality.

Dynamic contrast enhanced (DCE) imaging evaluates the vascularity in tumors which depends on its blood supply and its capillary permeability.

Diffusion weighted imaging (DWI) allows information about cellular density of the tumor.

MR spectroscopy provides information about the cellular metabolites within the prostate gland by displaying the relative concentrations of key chemical constituents such as citrate, choline and creatine.

Conventional anatomical MR imaging together with above mentioned MR technologies improves detection and localization of significant cancer, and can reliably characterize tumor biology.

This review presents a multiparametric MR imaging of the prostate cancer, that can allow optimal individual treatment planning, including focal therapy if possible, which would hopefully improve morbidity from prostate cancer and patients' quality of life, and also decrease mortality from prostate cancer.

Author: **Marsella Al-Amin, Ilia Diakov**

Subject: **Genitourinary**

Title: **The principles of low dose and ultra low 64 MDCT Urography**

Objective: As computed tomography urography is one of the most advanced imaging modalities and after 2000, it became one of the mainstream methods in uro-radiology our goal is to present our initial experience for the diagnosis of non malignant kidney diseases and congenital variants in the anatomy of the urinary system using low-dose protocols of research.

Method: There are different protocols based on the principles of ALARA. We have used three low-dose protocols of the study with no special preparation for the patients. We use three phases and late excretory one, after the introduction of contrast medium, using a single – bolus technique. Reconstructions are made on Maximim intensity projection and on Volume rendering.

Results: There are significant differences between the protocols, up to 81% dose reduction in measurable quantities CTDI and DLP, up to 60% dose reduction between the low-dose and ultra-low-dose protocols and up to 72 % reduction in effective dose which is estimation of radiation risk. At the same time the images have maintained their diagnostic quality.

Conclusion: CTU is detailed examination. As the radiation dose is an important issue, using low-dose and ultra-low-dose protocols of research we simultaneously save the image quality and reduce the radiation dose.